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EXPERIENCE IN THE USE OF A DIAGNOSTIC MAGNETOMETER IN THE EMERGENCY CLINIC*

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A new class of small and inexpensive diagnostic instruments designed in the Institute of Terrestrial Magnetism, the Ionosphere and Radiowave Propagation of the Russian Academy of Sciences — magnetic storm indicators — has laid the foundations for the practical use of magnetometers in urban conditions in the field of magnetobiology and medicine. The possibility, in principle, of using magnetometric equipment in conditions with quite a high level of technogenic electromagnetic interference is shown. The possibility of the clinic organizing its own service for monitoring the ambient electromagnetic situation in real time is demonstrated experimentally.

For several decades, study of heliogeophysical factors and their effect on living organisms, including man, has been pursued. Different science centres are engaged in research concerning the problem of the influence of natural electromagnetic fields on the plant and animal world [1–9]. It has now been reliably established that the degree of risk for persons suffering from cardiovascular conditions correlates with the level of solar activity [1, 7, 8]. According to published statistics the risk factor is minimal in years of the solar activity minimum to reach a maximum in the periods of rise and fall in solar activity. The heaviest magnetic storms and magnetospheric disturbances come in the period of rise and fall in solar activity, their frequency (number) being greater the higher the solar activity in the given year. The frequency of magnetic storms also depends on the time of the year and tends to increase in periods of the equinoxes [10].

A magnetic storm is a consequence of flares on the Sun and is accompanied by rapid (from one to tens of hours) change in the magnetic field with amplitudes at mid-latitudes from 100 to 500 nT and higher. The normal diurnal variations of the Earth's magnetic field do not exceed 50–70 nT. Investigations [11] have shown that during magnetic storms, in people suffering from hypertension the probability of a crisis developing is high. In the same periods there is an increase in the risk of development of myocardial infarct and the course of the disease is much more severe than in patients in whom the myocardial infarct develops in a relatively calm geophysical situation. Magnetic storms greatly promote the development of disturbances of cerebral blood circulation and aggravate the after-effects of a disease. The mortality maximum in

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cardiovascular pathology in the first 24 h after development of a magnetic storm was established by Gnevyshev [8], who attributed sudden death to a distinctive stress reaction of the sick body to change in the electromagnetic situation associated with change in solar activity. It is also known [1, 12] that in unfavourable heliogeophysical conditions myocardial infarct mortality is double that on calm days.

Forecasting helio- and geomagnetic disturbances is important not only for sick and enfeebled persons but also for those who by reason of their activity have to travel: car drivers, train drivers, aircraft dispatchers — all those who have to take key decisions against the clock. Unfortunately, the attempts of some mass information agencies to predict in advance so-called “unfavourable days” have met with little success. The existing predictions of magnetic storms published in the press diverge from the real data by 1–3 days so ruling out effective precaution (intake of drugs and reducing the strain for patients, change in the time of performing surgery and warning long-distance drivers of the raised danger of driving, etc.). Therefore, today in practical medicine there is even greater interest in the problem of the biotropy of natural electromagnetic fields, morbidity and mortality, problems of the working capacity of people in the work place, the problem of obtaining data on a real time scale, supplying therapeutic and health care institutions with very simple instruments capable of indicating the moments of onset and ending of a magnetic storm and inducing and fixing its course [6, 7].

The need to take measures of protection against the influence of a magnetic storm is primarily dictated by the need for means of detecting it real time and the conditions of a large industrial town with strong magnetic interference which may reach 1000 nT in amplitude. Highly sensitive (fixed and portable) instruments have now been devised for determining and indicating the amplitude of a magnetic storm in any region of the globe real time [13, 14]. They allow one to warn of the onset of a magnetic storm and may be used in practical medicine for rendering assistance to people with raised sensitivity to changes in the intensity of a magnetic storm. The technical characteristics and general form of the diagnostic magnetometers created and the instruments of a new class — magnetic storm indicators — are presented in [14, 15]. The comparative characteristics of various diagnostic magnetometer modifications have been tabulated [15].

WORK WITH INSTRUMENTS IN URBAN CONDITIONS

The main question in organizing and carrying out the work was elucidation of the possibility, in principle, of operation of a diagnostic magnetometer in the conditions of industrial interference of a city, in the presence of a high magnetic field gradient. Between 1990 and 1993 we carried out experimental-methodological work both in a number of cities with a high technogenic level surrounding the point of measurement and a high level of electromagnetic interference such as Moscow, Simferopol and Troitsk [15], for example, and in a number of spa towns (Yalta, Sudak, Kislovodsk, etc.), where the level of electromagnetic noise and interference is far lower [15–17]. Table 1 gives estimations of the maximum level of interference expressed in the parameters of the magnetic field (by the D-component of the Earth's magnetic field vector), of some of the points of our observations.

To register the results of the measurements of the magnetic field variations, the electromagnetic noise and pulse interference levels at all the points of measurement, we used as recorders standard automatic band recording potentiometers such as the KSP-4, N-39, N399 and others. This then allowed us to analyse the results of the measurements, compare them with the

Table 1. Comparative levels of technogenic electromagnetic interference experimentally recorded at the points of setting up the diagnostic magnetometers.

Town	Technogenic characteristics of the magnetic field at the point of measurement	
	Maximum level of pulse interference (nT)	Maximum field gradient (nT/m)
Moscow	20–100	500–1000
Troitsk	15–200	20–1000
Yalta	5–70	100–500
Kislovodsk	5–35	800–1000
Simferopol	50–80	700–1000

data of the Moscow Central Magnetic Observatory (CMO) sited in the territory of Troitsk (IZMIRAN).

In the course of the investigations diagnostic magnetometers were set up at points with a sufficiently high level of electromagnetic interference (see Table 1). It should be noted that, in some cases, by changing the location of the magnetometers and searching for the optimal siting point we were able to lower considerably the level of the acting electromagnetic interference on their magnetosensitive sensors. Thus, during the measurements at the Yalta seismostation located next to the children's polyclinic (Yalta) with a trolley bus line 20 m from it, it was noted that interference in the analogue trace of the magnetometer set up on the first floor of the building is essentially determined by migrating currents spreading at ground level. On moving the magnetosensitive sensor from ground level upwards by about 3–4 m, the amplitude of the interference acting from the trolley bus line fell by an order [17]. An example of a continuous (for 8 days) analogue trace of the D-component of the Earth's magnetic field vector at the Yalta seismostation as compared with the CMO trace is shown in Fig. 1. The Earth's magnetic field variations were measured in Yalta with the aid of the MF-01 magnetic storm indicator [14] and as compared with the CMO trace the measurements were about twice as crude although they quite well correlate (correlation coefficient $R = 0.85 \dots 0.9$) and in Fig. 1 all the characteristic features of these two curves are clearly seen.

An example of the registration of a very large magnetic storm between 9 and 12 May 1992 using the MF-01 magnetic storm indicator MAGIC set up on the sixth floor of a conventional sixteen storey residential building in Troitsk [15] is shown in Fig. 2. Here, the lower part of the figure gives information on the mean hourly values of the measured variations of the D-component of the Earth's magnetic field vector in the analogue display of the diagnostic magnetometer in real time. For comparison the upper part of Fig. 2 gives the trace of the magnetic storm obtained from the CMO D-variometer.

WORK WITH INSTRUMENTS IN THE CLINIC

The idea of using the magnetometer in clinical conditions grew out of the discussion of one of the authors Orayevskii with Kanonidi and Ruzhin. One of the first experimental diagnostic magnetometer prototypes was set up by us in 1991 in the laboratory of magnetobiology at the Resuscitation Department of the Central Clinical Hospital (CCH) No. 6 Medical Centre,

Fig. 1. Example of a continuous synchronous 8-day trace of the D-component of the vector of the Earth's magnetic field using diagnostic magnetometers set up in the Central Magnetic Observatory (CMO) (1) and at the Yalta Seismostation (2).

Moscow [15]. During the investigations we also came up against the problem of seeking the optimal site to set up diagnostic magnetometer magnetosensitive sensors. Having regard to the specifics of the work of the clinic, the large quantity of different types of electronic medical equipment, the presence of chaotically alternating magnetic masses (instruments, beds, etc.) in adjacent rooms and not subject to systemization and control, the constant work of loading lifts etc., we were able experimentally so to set up the diagnostic magnetometer as to lower to a maximum the level of constant and variable electromagnetic interference acting on it. During the investigations a constant express analysis was made of the surrounding noise situation and the results of measurement of the variations in the natural magnetic field were controlled by comparing them with the CMO data. At the initial stage of the work we wished to obtain answers to the following questions:

- (1) What are we actually measuring?
- (2) Which (in the presence of a fairly high magnetic field gradient in the room) of the components of the Earth's magnetic field vector do we register?
- (3) Which of the components of the Earth's magnetic field vector is easiest and most convenient to register in these conditions?
- (4) Is it possible to record a magnetic storm in the conditions of a clinic with a high level of technogenic and electromagnetic interference?
- (5) What is the maximum permissible level of electromagnetic interference at the point of setting up the sensor for it to record with confidence a magnetic storm?

In a series of methodological studies made in some rooms of the Resuscitation Department of the Central Clinical Hospital No. 6 Medical Centre we obtained, in the main, answers to the

Fig. 2. Example of the recording of a magnetic storm using the MF-04 diagnostic magnetometer MAGIC set up on the sixth floor of a conventional residential sixteen storey building on 9–12 May 1992. Upper part shows the trace of the magnetic storm obtained in the CMO (a). Horizontal broken lines show the levels corresponding to minor ($U_1, -U_1$), medium ($U_2, -U_2$) and major (U_3) magnetic storms. Lower part shows the 4-day trace of the mean hourly values of the variations of the D-component of the Earth's magnetic field vector on the diagnostic magnetometer analogue display (b).

questions posed. For example, an experiment showed that it is far easier in the conditions of the clinic to evaluate the intensity of a magnetic storm from the degree of the magnetic tendency. Since in the period of the magnetic storm the perturbation of the Earth's magnetic field sharply rises, as a rule it is manifest in a high amplitude of the fluctuations of all its components. In this case it is most convenient to trace the change in the direction of the plane of the magnetic meridian, that is change in the D-component of the Earth's magnetic field vector.

In the course of diagnostic magnetometer measurements in the CCH No. 6 Medical Centre the variations in the D-component of the Earth's magnetic field vector were recorded continuously and round the clock using an automatic recording potentiometer on a paper diagram band the run-through speed of which for convenience of comparison with the CMO data was taken as standard equal to 20 mm/h. For the methodological study, we simultaneously used from one to three magnetometers. The main diagnostic magnetometer used as magnetic storm indicator worked in the Resuscitation Department of the clinic in a continuous regime for more than 2 years and showed itself to be a reliable instrument, easy to operate. This enabled the laboratory of magnetobiology to conduct a whole series of studies of a methodological and research nature and work out the necessary recommendations for identifying and treating magneto-dependent cardiological patients [18]. The use of the diagnostic magnetometer made it possible for the first time to organize in the clinic in Moscow its own service for monitoring the surrounding electromagnetic situation in real time, to have a constant stream of data on the existing perturbation of the magnetic field and undertake timely therapy of magneto-dependent patients at the start of a magnetic storm. As an illustration, Fig. 3 gives a fragment of the analogue trace in

Fig. 3. Fragment of the continuous synchronous 2-day trace on 2 and 3 February 1992 of the D-component of the Earth's magnetic field vector using diagnostic magnetometers set up in the CMO (1) and the CCH No. 3 Medical Centre (2).

the period of a day with a fair degree of magnetic disturbance. The trace was obtained by us in the CCH No. 6 Medical Centre as compared with the CMO data. The fragment makes clear all the characteristic features of the Earth's magnetic field variations registered in Moscow and Troitsk — two measuring points about 50 km apart in the meridional direction. The trace in Moscow clearly shows the level of electromagnetic noise and interference registered by the diagnostic magnetometer in the daytime and evening hours the mean amplitude of which did not exceed 20–30 nT. At night time in the trace of the magnetic field in Moscow the interference level appreciably fell to an amplitude of not more than 3–5 nT.

In October 1992 in a room occupied by the climatology group of the Pyatigorsk Health Resort and Physiotherapy Research Institute (PHRPRI) in Kislovodsk we simultaneously set up two types of diagnostic magnetometer: the MF-04 MAGIC and MF-03 MAGIC magnetic storm indicators [14]. The work was carried out as part of the service for monitoring the electromagnetic situation in real time in the conditions of the clinic and in a spa zone. The data on the technogenic situation surrounding both points of measurements are presented in Table 1. It should be noted that the magnetometric apparatus was set up on the third floor of the three-storey building of the clinic, in the loft, the roof of which was covered with galvanized iron and sets were positioned on the first floor boiler room (about 10–12 m down).

Figure 4 shows a fragment of the analogue trace obtained in the PHRPRI at two points of measurement located at the same level but about 3 m apart. For comparison we give here the

Fig. 4. Fragment of a continuous synchronous 2-day trace on 10 and 11 December 1992 of the D-component of the Earth's magnetic field vector using diagnostic magnetometers set up at three different points of measurement: in the CMO (1) and in the PHRPRI and at Kislovodsk (2 and 3).

Fig. 5. Fragment of the continuous synchronous trace of the D-component of the Earth's magnetic field vector using diagnostic magnetometers set up at four different points of measurement: in the CMO (1) and in the PHRPRI in Kislovodsk (2 and 3) and in the CCH No. 6 Medical Centre (4).

record of variation in the magnetic tendency obtained at the same time in the CMO. Figure 4 shows that the electromagnetic interference level here was very low, not more than 2–5 nT, even in daytime, since nearby there are no industrial establishments nor transport facilities requiring electric power.

The fragment of the simultaneous record of the Earth's magnetic field variations at the four points of measurement in the period of a minor magnetic storm is shown in Fig. 5. Here in the experiment we simultaneously used four different diagnostic magnetometer modifications, three being set up in the clinics of Moscow and Kislovodsk and one in a non-magnetic pavilion (CMO) of IZMIRAN in Troitsk. All the traces well correlate, the trace of the magnetic field in Moscow (CCH No. 6 Medical Centre) clearly mirroring the level of daytime technogenic interference virtually absent in the traces of the other instruments.

CONCLUSION

The experience gained by us in the use of diagnostic magnetometers of different types and designs in the clinic allows the following conclusions to be drawn:

(1) a new class of diagnostic magnetometric instruments has been constructed — magnetic storm indicators;

(2) the possibility, in principle, of using magnetometric equipment in conditions with quite a high level of technogenic electromagnetic interference has been demonstrated;

(3) the possibility of registering magnetic storms in the conditions of the clinic has been experimentally shown;

(4) the possibility, in principle, of organizing in the clinic its own service for monitoring the surrounding electromagnetic situation in real time has been shown;

(5) diagnostic magnetometers may be used in the clinic not only as magnetic storm indicators but as an instrument for identifying magneto-dependent persons. as an indicator of the

electromagnetic situation surrounding them, as an instrument for undertaking research in a magnetic chamber, etc.; and

(6) the new magnetic storm indicator models created as a result of the experimental-methodological and research work undertaken are small in size, economical, quite simple to operate and service, and may be recommended for equipping medical institutions.

Various diagnostic magnetometer types are continuing to be used by us in Moscow, Yalta (the region of the Nikitskii Botanical Garden) and Kislovodsk constantly and in a continuous regime.

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